

Between the Memo and the Mandate

Institutional Perspectives on Public Access Readiness

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Executive Summary

Beginning on or before 31 December 2025, all recipients of United States federal research funding will be required to make their federally funded scholarly outputs, including scientific data, freely available via public access venues with no delays or embargos. These requirements arise from the 2022 Memorandum on Ensuring Free, Immediate and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research issued by the US Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP), commonly referred to as the “Nelson memo.”

This paper reports the results from the work of the NSF-funded project “Investigating ‘reasonable costs’ to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data” (NSF Grant No. 2330827, 2023-2025). We summarize some of the general characteristics of our research partners and the results of two surveys focused on campus-level and unit-level responses to federal public access mandates. Additional analysis based on workflow research and interviews with these research partners is forthcoming in June, 2025.¹

Our key takeaways from these surveys include:

- Infrastructure that can support public access mandates, in particular institutional repositories, is widely implemented across the US institutions we surveyed.
- Policy support at the institutional level is less widespread, for reasons that are unclear.
- More institutions provide financial support for meeting public access requirements related to publications than for research data, but this may be at least in part because many generalist and discipline-based data repositories are currently free of charge to use.
- Libraries are more likely than other campus units to report the impact of federal public access mandates as “noticeable” or “transformational.”

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15611424>

Background

Project Overview

The Office of Science Technology and Policy's (OSTP) Nelson memo, issued in August 2022, requires recipients of US federal research grants to make the publications and data resulting from that research freely and publicly available without embargoes. With a deadline for agency policies to be implemented by December 31, 2025,² our team sought to investigate how research-performing institutions will respond, what will be deemed a "reasonable" cost of compliance, and who will pay. One pillar of our work towards [understanding the reasonable costs of public access](#)³ has been working with 27⁴ research-performing institutions (colleges, universities and research laboratories) to understand their plans for meeting this challenge.

Here, we report on the general characteristics of our research partners (see Appendix for a list of institutions), and the results of two surveys we designed and conducted in 2024. These surveys focused on campus-level and unit-level responses to federal public access mandates. The campus-level survey was distributed to our primary contact at each institution. We received responses from 24 institutions, 20 of which were completed by a representative of the institution's library. The primary contacts were asked to identify at least three units within their organization to complete the unit-level survey. We received a total of 80 responses from 25 institutions and classified the responding units as Library (27 responses), IT/Computing (17 responses), Office of Research (28 responses), College-level office (7 responses), and Office of the President, Provost (1 response). Multiple responses from the same (or similar) units within an institution were permitted. Responses for the surveys were submitted between April and October of 2024.

Institutional characteristics

One of our goals for this project was to examine whether emerging public access requirements equally impact institutions of different types. We collected some basic demographic and financial data on participating institutions from the National Science

² The National Institutes of Health opted to move up the effective date of their public access policy to 1 July, 2025 (Battcharya 2025).

³ This work was supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 2330827. Any opinions, findings, conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

⁴ Note that not all of the institutions participated in the survey we report on here.

Foundation’s National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics (NCSES)⁵ and the National Center for Education Statistics Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (IPEDS).⁶ In particular, we looked at each institution’s Carnegie classification⁷ in IPEDS (if available) and total research and development (R&D) expenditures reported in NCSES (as a proxy for research funding). Our original intent was to work with as broad a range of post-secondary institutions as possible, including community colleges, tribal colleges, and historically black colleges and universities. As we spoke with potential participants, we heard that many smaller and less well-endowed institutions were under exceptional stress and simply did not have the bandwidth to participate. Despite our best efforts, we found ourselves working with a large group of doctoral universities: 17 with high or very high research activity and two doctoral/professional universities.

Due in part to the constellation of institutions we worked with, we found “total R&D expenditures” to be our strongest way to understand the impact of the policies across the range of institutions we worked with. We broke the institutions out into four categories based on their R&D spending (Table 1). We use these categories as our funding groups throughout this paper.

R&D spending class	Count of institutions
<\$10M	5
\$10-100M	6
\$100M-1B	7

Table 1. R&D spending classification of participating institutions. All NCSES data were from 2022, with the exception of University of Maryland (the most recent available data was from 2018). R&D spending for the Cary Institute of Ecosystem Studies was inferred from their publicly available 2023 financial statement (total operating expenses, likely an overestimate).⁸

⁵ <https://nces.nsf.gov/>

⁶ <https://nces.ed.gov/ipeds/datacenter/InstitutionByName.aspx>

⁷ <https://carnegieclassifications.acenet.edu/>

⁸ <https://www.caryinstitute.org/about/financial-statements>

Infrastructure and policy support for federal public access mandates

To place activity and investment in context, we asked respondents to indicate at what stages their units are actively engaged in the research process (Figure 1; see Appendix for definitions). Libraries report substantial engagement in all phases except project closeout and compliance. The pattern for IT/Computing units is similar, with more involvement in the planning and execution of research, but less in making research outputs broadly available. Offices of Research tend to be most involved in the planning and closeout phases. Involvement of College-level offices appears lower across the entire process, with the exception of the planning phase. We do not include the single response we received from an Office of the President or Provost, although that respondent indicated involvement in every phase.

Figure 1. Engagement by unit across the research life cycle, from the unit-level survey. The count of responses for each unit type is noted in the legend, and more than one unit of the same type at the same institution may respond to the survey. Research phase definitions are listed in the Appendix.

Infrastructure support (institutional repository (IR), data repository, digital preservation infrastructure) appears to be higher than most types of policy support related to public access mandates (Figure 2A). Interestingly, 100% of respondents in every funding group (except the \$10-100M group) indicate support for an IR. We do note that for data repository support, our survey question did not attempt to distinguish between a standalone data repository, an IR that also accepts data, or membership services provided by external data repositories. In general, data repository support increases by funding group, as does support for digital preservation infrastructure. Some institutions did express concern about having the resources to adequately support public access mandates, with one respondent commenting, "I'd really, really like to see more documentation, and/or tools, directed towards the needs and capacity of smaller, non-R1 institutions."

Open access policies, which should promote practices consistent with public access mandates, are widespread among institutions with lower R&D funding (more than 75% of those with <\$10M, and range from 17-57% for the other funding categories, Figure 2B). We do find it very interesting that less emphasis seems to be placed on other policies related to public access (publication deposit, and sharing and deposit policies for data), and it would be interesting to explore issues such as whether institutions consider local policies to be redundant with the emergence of funder policies, and whether policies related to data sharing lag those for publications even well more than a decade after the early federal data management sharing and planning policies took effect.

When we take a closer look at the ways in which institutions provide financial support for making articles and research data publicly available, we see more investment in publishing articles than research data (Figure 3). Support for article processing charges doesn't follow an obvious pattern across funding groups, but the use of read and publish agreements is noticeably more common among institutions with more research funding.

Figure 2A, B. Infrastructure and policy support by funding group, from the campus-level survey.

Figure 3. Article and data publication support by funding group, from the campus-level survey.

When it comes to research data, support for data deposit fees appears to be relatively low. Institutional support for data repository memberships is higher for better-funded institutions, and may explain why deposit fee support is low, as researchers from member institutions would pay no deposit fees. In addition, as we found in an earlier study of the cost of providing public access to research data (Steinhart & Skinner, 2024), many data repositories charge no fees at all. Where data repository memberships are supported, this funding typically comes from the library, although a couple of college-level offices and offices of research also report contributions.

Provision and monitoring of funding to cover article processing charges (APCs) and managing support requests from researchers falls mostly to Libraries and College-level offices, although a non-trivial proportion of Research offices and Offices of the President or Provost also contribute (Figure 4). Given their central role in negotiating and managing subscription agreements for their institutions, it is not surprising that Libraries have primary responsibility for supporting, funding and monitoring the use of publishing agreements that may be leveraged to meet public access requirements (Figure 5). The use of these agreements also appears to be more widespread than institutional support for APCs (Figures 4, 5). Note that no support for public access to publications was reported for IT/Computing units.

Figure 4. Unit involvement in support for article processing charges (APCs), from the campus-level survey.

Figure 5. Unit involvement in support for publishing agreements, from the campus-level survey.

The impact and evolution of public access support

The Nelson memo of 2022 was preceded by an earlier public access mandate, the Holdren memo of 2013 (Office of Science and Technology Policy 2013), and one question we were interested in exploring is the degree to which each of the two public access memos prompted change across research-performing organizations. We do want to note that the survey asked about strategies for public access support at different points in time relative to the publication of the two memos. The impact of the Holdren memo on research-performing institutions is, by now, reasonably well-understood. At the time of our survey, however, Nelson memo policies had yet to take effect, and institutions no doubt varied in the progress they had made towards developing their strategies. That said, the overall patterns look reasonably similar for both memos (Figures 6, 7), with relatively low impact (less change) for Offices of the President or Provost and College-level offices. A significant number of Offices of Research report minor changes after both memos. Change is also not particularly dramatic for IT/Computing units, but the Nelson memo appears to be having slightly more impact than the Holdren memo. Libraries report the most change following both memos, at somewhat similar levels for both.

Another way to view the impact of the memos is through investment in services related to public access requirements. Libraries and IT/Computing units reported additional investment more frequently than other units, so we chose to focus this question on the change in investment activity in services provided by these units driven by both the Holdren and Nelson memos.

Figure 6. Impact of the Holdren memo on operations by unit, from the unit-level survey. More than one response was allowed from each unit type at an institution; the count of responses for each unit type is indicated on the x-axis.

Figure 7. Impact of the Nelson memo on operations by unit, from the unit-level survey. More than one response was allowed from each unit type at an institution; the count of responses for each unit type is indicated on the x-axis.

For libraries, the most obvious observation is that even though support for public access to publications increased after both memos, a relatively large number of respondents also indicated no change in support for publications following the Nelson memo (Figure 8A). One possible explanation is that with final funder policies due at the end of 2025, the change has yet to arrive, but another is that libraries established their basic strategies at the time of the Holdren memo. While the Nelson memo expands the public access mandates to include the research of all federal funders, Holdren included the largest. It is possible that the additional support required by the Nelson memo is for the long tail of research supported by smaller federal funders, and this didn't necessitate much change on the part of libraries. Investment in support for public access to data is comparable across both memos. For both publications and data, and across both memos, Libraries report investing in additional services somewhat more frequently than in technical infrastructure or staffing.

Investment by IT/Computing units isn't strictly comparable to library investments because there were fewer responses to the survey from these units (17 IT/Computing, 27 Library), but we thought it noteworthy that the Nelson memo seems to be prompting more investment in services related to data than the Holdren memo did, primarily in technical infrastructure (Figure 8B).

Figure 8A, B. Additional investment made by Libraries (A) and IT/Computing (B) to support Holdren and Nelson memo requirements, from the unit-level survey, which had 25 library responses and 17 IT/Computing responses. More than one response was allowed from each unit type at an institution.

Meeting the moment: Partnerships and gaps

We sought to understand how the units we surveyed work with one another, and what participants felt they and their constituents would most need to know to meet the moment.

We asked participants in the unit-level survey to describe partnerships with other units on their campus, and coded the responses to align unit types (those that did not align with the unit types in the study were coded as “other”). Because we had more responses from Libraries and Offices of Research than from other units, we cannot really claim any one unit type is more predisposed to partnerships than other units, but we can report that Libraries, Offices of Research, and IT/Computing units partner more frequently with each other than with other unit types (Table 2).

Responding unit	Reported partner: College-level office(s)	Reported partner: IT/Computing	Reported partner: Library	Reported partner: Office of Research	Reported partner: Other
College-level office	N/A	0	1	0	0
IT/Computing	1	N/A	4	4	0
Library	5	9	N/A	9	4
Office of Research	0	6	9	N/A	1
Office of the President, Provost	0	1	1	1	0

Table 2. Partnerships between units on the same campus to support the requirements of the Nelson memo from the unit-level survey. More than one response from the same unit type within an institution was allowed.

Finally, we asked units what they think their stakeholders most needed to know to effectively meet the requirements of public access mandates, and what forms of guidance

would be most useful. We coded the free text responses and offer some concluding observations. First, far and away, the specifics of how to meet emerging policies for both publications and data are extremely important to Libraries, Offices of Research, and IT/computing units. Specific concerns include solidifying their understanding of the scope of public access policies, knowing where researchers should deposit their research outputs, understanding requirements related to format, embargo, retention, and sensitive data, and determining whether existing infrastructure and services are adequate. Also important is a better understanding of allowable costs and budgeting, and who will pay. The concerns regarding cost and budgeting are especially important to College-level Offices, Offices of the President or Provost, and Offices of Research. Compliance management was notably important to Offices of Research. And last, workflow management tools and decision trees come up frequently as an area where guidance materials would be useful.⁹

In spite of the more equivocal responses (for some units and institutions) earlier in the survey regarding the impact of the two public access memos and what additional investments institutions are making, it is clear that participants have many questions about how this will all come together as the requirements go into effect. At the time that we write this (well after the two surveys were administered), we are witnessing a dramatic reorientation of the scientific agenda and funding support in the US. This introduces additional uncertainty into the picture, complicating planning efforts both on the part of research funding agencies and the recipients of that funding. These developments leave us wondering whether stakeholders will be adequately prepared to support public access to research as the policies take effect. Likewise, we (and many of the surveyed institutions) continue to wonder how compliance will be assessed and whether noncompliance will carry penalties.

⁹ Invest in Open Infrastructure has developed guidance on developing and documenting workflows for sponsored projects that will be released in June, 2025, at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15611424>.

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Appendix

Participating institutions

This list reflects those institutions that participated in one or both surveys. Additional institutions participated in other aspects of the project, but are not listed here.

Cary Institute of Ecosystem Studies	Pennsylvania State University
Charles R. Drew University of Medicine and Science	Pepperdine University
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory	Purdue University
Dartmouth College	SUNY Brockport
Grand Valley State University	SUNY Geneseo
Indiana University, Bloomington	SUNY Oswego
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	University of Chicago
Michigan State University	University of Maryland, College Park
Middlebury College	University of Minnesota
Morgan State University	University of Wisconsin, Madison
North Carolina A & T State University	West Virginia University
Northwestern University	William & Mary
The Ohio State University, Main Campus	Yale University

Research phase definitions

- **Planning, design, and start up of research projects:** Developing data management and/or sharing plans, developing IRB protocols, ensuring grant proposal compliance, planning towards deposit and preservation of research outputs.
- **Research output collection, storage, and management:** Developing documentation of data/research outputs, creating quality control mechanisms, managing active data/other research outputs.
- **Making research outputs broadly available:** Making decisions about what data/other research outputs to share or host, selecting or applying licenses to data/other research outputs, creating persistent identifiers.
- **Research output sharing or retention:** Distribution, preservation, archiving, and provision of long-term access, and any additional actions that support those operations.
- **Project closeout and compliance:** Ensuring funding agency requirements have been met, ensuring institutional compliance requirements are met, final reporting.

Contributor roles

We use the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to specify collaborators' contributions:
<https://credit.niso.org/>.

Lauren Collister, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5767-8486>: Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing - review & editing

Jennifer Kemp, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4086-3196>: Writing – review & editing

Sarah Lippincott, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5700-5844>: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing

Katherine Skinner, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0139-7524>: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing

Gail Steinhart, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2441-1651>: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing – review & editing

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